

TREND IN FOCUS

ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY AS A TREND IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING

Dr. Filippo Pusterla, Dr. Miriam Hänni, Prof. Dr. Lukas Graf

April 2026

The Federal Government's Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 positions education as central to achieving its sustainability goals. Vocational education and training (VET) is particularly well placed to contribute in this regard, given its close links with the world of work. As sustainability becomes embedded in VET, the VET partners face both opportunities and challenges. What role do the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability currently play in VET? Where can VET contribute to sustainability, and what tensions exist between these three dimensions? This short report examines these questions.

Summary

- As multiple planetary boundaries are exceeded, the urgency of sustainability is increasing. VET is a key lever for embedding environmental responsibility within economic and social frameworks.
- In Swiss VET, sustainability is framed as a cross-cutting theme intended to systematically integrate the three dimensions of environmental, social and economic sustainability.
- The three dimensions of sustainability interact in ways that create both opportunities through mutually reinforcing effects and potential trade-offs when progress in one dimension undermines another.
- These interactions can be clearly illustrated by the example of the career choice process: environmentally motivated interest in 'green' occupations among young people can be reinforced where these offer strong economic prospects. Trade-offs may arise, however, when environmental considerations in career decisions are overridden by social and economic factors.
- VET stakeholders are tasked with identifying, balancing and addressing trade-offs between the sustainability dimensions in ways that contribute to sustainable development over the long term.

Introduction

Public awareness of sustainability has grown significantly in recent decades. This is partly because the consequences of environmental developments – such as climate change, declining biodiversity and environmental pollution more generally – have become more evident.¹ Recent studies on the overuse of resources show that the Earth's environmental systems have reached the limits of their stability. At present, at least six of the nine planetary boundaries that define key environmental dimensions of the Earth system are being exceeded worldwide.² The current understanding of sustainability, however, is not limited to environmental aspects. Social dimensions of sustainability such as justice, diversity, inclusion and integration³, as well as economic aspects, such as resource consumption and the circular economy, are increasingly being discussed and applied – including in Switzerland.⁴

The Swiss Constitution commits the country to contributing to sustainable development and achieving a balanced relationship between nature and human activity over the long term while avoiding harmful impacts¹. Since 1997, the Swiss Federal Council has defined the priorities of its sustainability policy in the Sustainable Development Strategy. Through the 2030 Agenda, this strategy was incorporated into a clearly defined reference framework for sustainable development based on the 17 global goals of the United Nations (Sustainable Development Goals, SDGs).⁵ This is a complex and ambitious agenda that calls for gradual change and, in some cases, far-reaching transformation. Business and finance, research, innovation and education all play a key role in achieving the sustainability goals. Vocational education and training (VET) is particularly well placed to contribute, given its close links with the world of work. The workplace is not only a critical arena for sustainable development, as work activities consume substantial resources and energy and generate emissions, but also a setting in which important innovation and change processes can be initiated.⁶

Sustainability affects stakeholders in the VET system at multiple levels, as the next section illustrates. To better understand the resulting implications, this report starts by situating the concept of sustainability in the context of VET before outlining the most relevant themes at both national and international levels. Drawing on the example of the career choice process, it also demonstrates that sustainability in VET presents not only challenges, but also considerable potential.

Sustainability as a key concern for VET stakeholders

The Swiss VET system is characterised by the fact that responsibility for VET governance is shared by the federal government, the cantons and professional organisations, collectively referred to as the VET partners. In the academic literature, systems such as Switzerland's are described as collective VET systems.⁷ This collective system offers diverse opportunities to strengthen sustainability aspects, as all key stakeholders are involved and able to coordinate closely in this area.⁸

The VET partners in Switzerland engage with sustainability in various ways, including through discussions on vocational education and training for sustainable development (VETSD). Within VETSD, an overarching objective is to enable all stakeholders to shape learning processes and professional practice in ways that contribute to environmentally sound, socially equitable and economically viable development. Professional organisations play a pivotal role here, as they are responsible for the (further) development of professional profiles and training plans. This development process provides a key opportunity to integrate or further strengthen sustainability within

ⁱ See Articles 2 and 73.

occupations. This concerns not only newly created 'green occupations'ⁱⁱ, such as solar installer (Federal VET Diploma, FVETD) or solar technician (Federal VET Certificate, FVETC), but also occupations across the board. The most recent revision of retail training, for example, incorporated sustainability knowledge into the programme.ⁱⁱⁱ In the occupational development process, the primary concern for professional organisations is identifying the needs of companies so that the dual VET system continues to meet them. It is therefore crucial for professional organisations to strengthen competencies and content aligned with industry needs. Sustainability aspects therefore take on greater importance in the occupational development process where they are already in demand in industry or are expected to become more so, or where regulatory conditions – such as climate targets in certain sectors – make this necessary.

The federal government seeks to create incentives to ensure that sustainability is given greater consideration in the occupational development process. Following consultation with various stakeholders, the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) published its guidance on sustainable development in VET (*Orientierungshilfe Nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Berufsbildung*) in 2020. It is intended to serve as a resource for VET stakeholders in the occupational development process to help embed sustainability in occupations. In addition, the Federal Office for the Environment and the Federal Office of Energy have developed a practical guide that deepens the dimension of environmental responsibility by outlining concrete ways of integrating environmental, climate and energy competences into the occupational development process.¹² As a further instrument, SERI introduced a new funding priority of sustainable development in vocational and professional education and training (*Nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Berufs- und Weiterbildung*) in 2023. This funding priority follows a holistic approach, encompassing advisory services, financial support and knowledge transfer. Under this scheme, SERI now supports the possibility for professional organisations to obtain external expert advice on the sustainability dimensions of society and economy. This complements the existing advisory services on the environmental dimension, which continue to be delivered by subject specialists from the Federal Office for the Environment and the Federal Office of Energy. The voluntary funding includes a lump sum for analysis and advisory services that covers part of the process costs to ensure that all dimensions of sustainable development are taken into account in VET frameworks. There are therefore various state-level initiatives and advisory services in Switzerland aimed at strengthening the voluntary integration of sustainability in VET. Germany has taken a somewhat different approach, where sustainability has been mandatory in the occupational development process for new ordinances since 2021.¹³ The coming years will reveal the extent to which voluntary measures strengthen sustainability in VET, and whether more binding requirements, such as those in Germany, are more effective.

Sustainability is not only a concern for the VET partners in the occupational development process, but also for young people and companies. For young people in VET, the topic is relevant both in

ⁱⁱ Green occupations are, in the narrower sense, occupations that make a significant contribution to preserving, restoring or improving environmental quality. These include occupations that protect ecosystems and biodiversity, reduce energy, material and water consumption, contribute to the decarbonisation of the economy and avoid environmental impacts.⁹ A broader definition of 'green occupations' also encompasses occupations whose activities do not directly contribute to emissions reduction but are likely to be increasingly in demand because they provide goods and services needed for green activities.¹⁰ Ultimately, an even broader definition includes the potential to perform green activities, regardless of whether these are currently part of the occupational profile. 'Green occupations' therefore include not only traditional environmental occupations (such as gardener or forestry worker), but all activities with high transformation and innovation potential within a sustainable economy.¹¹

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2021/314/de>

terms of knowledge and in their everyday vocational experience and values. A recent study by SFUVET researchers points to an ambivalent relationship among young people towards sustainability.¹⁴ In companies that promote sustainable professional practice, learners acquire not only practical expertise, but also confidence and a sense of agency. Others, however, experience frustration when environmental considerations are overridden by economic priorities in everyday workplace practice. In the absence of positive learning experiences, sustainability may be perceived as largely beyond individual influence, or passive attitudes towards environmental crises may be reinforced. Vocational learning contexts therefore play a key role in shaping whether sustainability becomes a meaningful and actionable element of young people's professional practice.

Sustainability also matters to companies. For many of them, improving the efficiency of production processes and the use of resources is an ongoing concern. From a sustainability perspective, optimising such processes should consider not only short-term profitability, but also their environmental and societal implications, which may ultimately support long-term economic performance. For example, diversifying supply chains in times of global uncertainty may make economic sense while also benefiting the environment if it results in lower CO2 emissions. Similarly, careful workforce planning that seeks to avoid sustained employee overload can have a positive effect on long-term health, thereby strengthening social sustainability and contributing to long-term skills retention. In times of skills shortages, this represents a significant economic benefit.¹⁵

Sustainability as a concept and its relevance to VET

Environmental, social and economic aspects of sustainability have become an important field of policy action in the area of VET.¹⁶ SERI defines sustainability in the context of VET as follows: Sustainable development aims to enable economic performance and social solidarity within the Earth's carrying capacity, while giving equal, balanced and integrated consideration to these three dimensions.^{iv} This definition highlights the three core dimensions of sustainability: the *economic dimension* with a focus on economic performance, the *social dimension* with a focus on social solidarity, and the *environmental dimension* with a focus on the Earth's carrying capacity. The latter implies that all activities should take place within the – already heavily strained – environmental limits of the Earth.¹⁹

The definition used by SERI underscores that the three dimensions of sustainability should not be considered in isolation but in integrated form – in other words, as interconnected. This corresponds to the *three-pillars model* of sustainability (see Fig. 1), which is one of the most widely known sustainability models both generally²⁰ and in VET²¹. Often depicted as a Venn diagram, this model emphasises that dependencies and interactions exist between the three dimensions at local, regional and global levels. In this sense, development can only be regarded as fully sustainable if all three dimensions are adequately taken into account.

The three-pillars model highlights the potential for synergies between the dimensions. Making an occupation more environmentally oriented, for example, can simultaneously increase its attractiveness, help companies attract skilled workers and improve economic efficiency. At the same time, trade-offs may arise between the dimensions if progress in one undermines another. This may occur, for example, when a shift towards more environmentally oriented work processes increases production costs to such an extent that the company's economic viability is threatened. The model calls on VET stakeholders to consider the three dimensions of sustainability as a whole, thereby helping to ensure that the living conditions of future generations are not compromised.

^{iv} SERI's definition follows that of the United Nations Brundtland Commission.^{17,18}

Figure 1: Three-pillars model of sustainability

Source: Own illustration, OBS SFUVET, based on Barbier (1987).²⁰

The implementation of the three-pillars model in VET can be illustrated through a hypothetical learning assignment for heating building services planners (FVETD) tasked with designing an app-controlled smart home heating system. From a holistic sustainability perspective, the objective could be to use energy more efficiently and thereby reduce CO₂ emissions (environmental dimension), to lower energy costs (economic dimension), and to ensure that the new technology is easy to use for all segments of society – including those with limited familiarity with or restricted access to digital technologies (social dimension).

The following section presents relevant findings from OBS trend monitoring activities to further examine the three dimensions of sustainability and their interplay.

Environmental, social and economic sustainability in OBS trend monitoring

An analysis of trend monitoring activities conducted by the Swiss Observatory for Vocational Education and Training (OBS trend monitoring; see info box) provides insight into which sustainability aspects are increasingly discussed in the VET literature. Compared with the start of the monitoring in 2018, the megatrend of sustainability is now addressed far more frequently in the literature considered. Figure 2 illustrates, in highly simplified form, the dominant themes within the megatrend of sustainability identified in the OBS monitoring pool and assigns them to the three dimensions. The following content analysis is intended to provide VET stakeholders with guidance on how sustainability aspects in VET could be strengthened across the different dimensions – for example, in the development or further development of occupations or within everyday company-based training.

OBS trend monitoring info box

OBS trend monitoring activities identify relationships between current megatrends in VET and key elements of the VET system. These activities are based on a pool of national and international publications from practice, research and policy (see [Monitoring method and process](#)). One of the megatrends analysed within OBS trend monitoring activities is sustainability. The analysis of the sustainability megatrend presented here draws on the sources of the literature monitoring activities (see [Literature monitoring](#)), supplemented selectively with additional relevant literature.

As illustrated in Figure 2, two themes are central within the **environmental dimension** in the sustainability literature analysed. The first area concerns *competence development* among learners and training staff in the context of VETSD. It addresses, among other things, which competences learners, training staff and other skilled professionals require in order to act sustainably, and how these ‘sustainability competences’ can best be fostered in VET. The literature indicates a degree of consensus that sustainability competences should be developed within concrete occupational contexts rather than through abstract, stand-alone learning situations.^{6, 22} Strengthening learners’ sustainability competences therefore requires sustainability to be embedded structurally in VET – for example, within curricula as part of VETSD.²³

Figure 2: Key sustainability themes in OBS trend monitoring activities

Source: Own illustration based on OBS trend monitoring activities

A concept for environmental education initiated by SFUVET on behalf of the Federal Office for the Environment illustrates how this could be implemented concretely at the company-based learning centre.²⁴ In the programme developed, all learners complete a three-part module on environmental topics during their apprenticeship. They explore issues such as mobility, energy and recycling, link these topics to company practice and develop their own solutions.²⁴ This makes sustainability a continuous educational theme within the company throughout the apprenticeship, with the aim of strengthening learners’ green skills – that is, their sustainability competences – directly within their own occupational context. This can contribute directly to *more environmentally conscious practices* among learners, which represents the second theme prominently discussed in the literature within the environmental dimension. This area focuses on how employees can be sensitised through continuing education and reskilling to adopt more resource-efficient practices in their occupation and beyond.²⁵ In this way, existing occupations can become ‘greener’ by replacing environmentally harmful activities with more environmentally sustainable ones. In addition, entirely new ‘green’ occupations have emerged in VET in recent years, such as the previously mentioned occupations in the solar sector.^{26,27}

In relation to the **social dimension** of sustainability, the literature primarily discusses the *health and well-being* of learners as well as *equal opportunities and pathways* within the VET system. Within the thematic area of *health and well-being*, the focus lies on managing psychological strain in the workplace. Learners spend most of their time in companies and encounter operational processes that may be perceived as stressful.²¹ Proactively supportive education institutions and

companies²², as well as increased awareness among teachers and trainers of learner diversity,²³ therefore play an important role in learners' health and well-being. An important aspect of *equal opportunities and pathways* within the VET system is the availability of structural measures such as bridging programmes or pre-apprenticeships that support young people in their transition into VET²⁴, as well as provisions for high-achieving learners, such as the vocational baccalaureate.²⁸ The literature also addresses the inclusion of learners with disabilities²⁵ and of young people facing, for example, linguistic or social challenges. Successful inclusion notably requires appropriate preparation and training for teachers and trainers.^{29,30} Gender-related issues, such as gender-(a)typical career choices³¹ or disadvantages in educational or employment trajectories based on gender³², represent further important topics that could be given greater attention in everyday VET practice.

Aspects of social and environmental sustainability frequently also affect the **economic dimension** of sustainability. Measures to combat climate change, for example, directly affect industry and the economy, including in terms of skills needs, new technologies and additional costs. At the same time, the economy is the most obvious driver of climate change and in many areas has a markedly negative impact on the environmental dimension, for example through greenhouse gas emissions or high resource consumption. This can give rise to trade-offs between the different dimensions.¹⁴ In VET practice, however, greater emphasis is typically placed on reconciling economic efficiency with environmental sustainability or social inclusion, which is why specific conflicts receive less attention in the literature analysed. Discussion focuses primarily on the *conditions shaping the environmental transformation* of the economy and on questions of *sustainable business development*. In discussions on *sustainable business development*, particular attention is paid to the role companies play in promoting sustainable development within VET, for example in relation to corporate social responsibility or support for the circular economy.^{4, 33, 34} Contributions addressing the *conditions shaping the environmental transformation* of the economy examine how the economy can concretely enable change, for example through the development of new technologies such as hydrogen technology.³⁵

Policy plays a decisive role in shaping framework conditions by defining the parameters within which the economy – and indirectly VET – can operate. Subsidies introduced in various Swiss cantons and municipalities for the energy-efficient renovation of buildings, as well as the partial ban on fossil heating systems, directly contribute to environmental transformation by reducing CO₂ emissions in the medium term. At the same time, these changing framework conditions have led to a sharp increase in orders and a high demand for skilled workers in certain occupational fields. This example illustrates that the necessary adaptation of the economy towards more environmentally sustainable technologies and practices in response to climate change increases demand for skilled workers in 'green' occupations or in occupations requiring 'green' competences. VET plays an important role in meeting this future demand for skilled workers, as it is primarily responsible for training the skilled workforce of tomorrow in Switzerland.³⁶

This brief literature-based overview shows that the three dimensions of sustainability – environmental, social and economic – are not merely theoretical concepts, but integral elements shaping VET practice. One area in which the interplay between these dimensions becomes especially apparent is career choice.

Sustainability and career choice

The career choice process marks a pivotal moment in VET – including from a sustainability perspective. In a dual system, environmental, social and economic considerations can significantly influence career decisions, both for the young people making those choices and for the companies

and sectoral organisations reliant on recruiting future skilled workers. This process provides a useful example for examining the role that the three dimensions of sustainability play for different stakeholders and the opportunities and trade-offs that may arise.

When considering the **environmental dimension** of sustainability, the question arises as to the extent to which young people's environmental awareness influences their career choice. From a scientific perspective, however, the concrete effects of attitudes towards environmental issues on career choice remain relatively under-researched, and the available evidence is partly contradictory. A recent study examining the influence of the 'Fridays for Future' climate protests on the career choices of young people in Switzerland³⁷ shows that in regions where participation in such protests was particularly high, young people tended to display a greater willingness to choose apprenticeships in occupations with the potential to contribute to environmental protection.³⁷ Another study finds that, in Germany, despite an overall decline in the number of applicants for apprenticeships, the number of newly filled apprenticeship positions in occupations involving environmentally or climate-friendly activities increased between 2013 and 2022.³⁶ The precise reasons for such developments are, however, often difficult to determine. One possible explanation is that young people view 'green' occupations as offering secure long-term prospects, which enhances their appeal. A study conducted in Germany among learners at a technically oriented vocational college points in a different direction. It shows that the majority of respondents did not pursue intrinsically societal sustainability motives when selecting a (training) company, but instead based their decision primarily on traditional occupational and company-related criteria such as working atmosphere, salary, career prospects or the nature of the work itself.³⁸ Further nuance is provided by a recent study among farmers in Switzerland. This study indicates an ambivalent relationship among young people towards sustainability.³⁹ While learners demonstrate broad knowledge of sustainability and recognise the diverse contributions agriculture can make, for example in location-adapted production and the promotion of biodiversity, their understanding often remains incomplete, particularly with regard to global interdependencies and the role of the food system. They also tend to regard Swiss agriculture as already highly sustainable and see little additional need for action to meet global sustainability goals.

This mixed picture points to possible courses of action for professional associations, which can play an important role in supporting young people's career orientation. Some are already taking proactive steps and seeking to position themselves accordingly. Associations with a link to environmental issues, such as 'Umwelt', aim to engage with young people's sensitivities in this regard and clearly outline the future prospects offered by environmental occupations.⁴⁰ For example, this professional organisation provides clear and accessible guidance on possible career pathways within the field: following initial VET as a farmer (FVETD) or drainage technologist (FVETD), learners can pursue attractive tertiary qualifications such as environmental consultant (professional examination) or technician in energy and environment (college of higher education).

The career choice process relates to the **economic dimension** in terms of the opportunity to choose occupations that offer the best possible long-term employment and salary prospects. According to a survey conducted as part of the SwissSkills 2023 competition, many young people are less concerned with the starting salary and place greater emphasis on career progression and development opportunities.⁴¹ Young people also take into account the overall economic viability of occupations, particularly those that may be strongly affected by economic or technological developments. A recent analysis from Switzerland shows, for example, that the emergence of ChatGPT has reduced young people's interest in occupations requiring certain cognitive tasks and high levels of language proficiency – that is, occupations that can to some extent be replaced by AI.⁴² By contrast, sustainable economic sectors (e.g. renewable energy and environmental technology) are

perceived as more crisis-resistant and more attractive.⁴³ Young people's preferences in the career choice process are of particular interest to companies. In times of skilled labour shortages and a projected demographic increase in the number of young people leaving compulsory education in several cantons, companies stand to benefit if they take young people's values and attitudes into account when marketing their apprenticeship places. With regard to sustainability within occupations, this could mean communicating their contributions in this area more explicitly. The potential of such an approach is illustrated by a recent Danish study examining how companies in the electrical and plumbing installation sectors can successfully highlight the green aspects of these occupations when recruiting young people.⁴⁴

The **social dimension** also plays a role in the career choice process and, as our OBS trend monitoring activities show, is closely linked to issues such as equality of opportunity, social cohesion and working conditions. A relevant factor in this regard is the extent to which a VET system provides individually suitable training options for different needs. Two-year VET programmes leading to a Federal VET Certificate, for example, can enable structurally disadvantaged young people to obtain an initial recognised qualification and thereby contribute to greater equality of opportunity. These qualifications not only facilitate entry into the primary labour market, but also create opportunities to progress to an appropriate further qualification and complete it successfully.⁴⁵ Similarly, the preparatory apprenticeship programme can prepare refugees and provisionally admitted migrants for an apprenticeship and for integration into the Swiss labour market, thereby positively influencing the career choice process. In this sense, these programmes support sustainable career choices and contribute to social justice and cohesion. The social dimension also manifests itself in the career choice process through health and safety aspects of apprenticeship occupations. An ongoing study shows that health and safety at work are treated as secondary considerations in the training plans of certain occupations.⁴⁶ This is linked to issues of social justice where some young people systematically gain access only to apprenticeship places in which such health and safety aspects are partly neglected. More broadly, social considerations also constitute an important criterion for young people when choosing a career. The same SwissSkills survey highlights that a positive working environment and meaningful work are likewise given considerable weight by young people.⁴¹

The three dimensions of sustainability outlined in relation to career choice (environmental, economic and social) cannot be considered in isolation, as interactions may occur between them. Aspects from different sustainability dimensions may reinforce one another in the career choice process, for example where young people's environmentally motivated interest in 'green' occupations is strengthened by the economic prospects these occupations often offer. At the same time, the different dimensions may also pull in different directions, for example when environmental and social considerations compete. Research from Scandinavian countries suggests that during adolescence, pro-environmental attitudes may temporarily decline where they conflict with material desires linked to social belonging.^{14, 47, 48} In such situations, the need for social connectedness at this stage of life appears to limit the incorporation of environmental sustainability into young people's career choices.

The interactions between the three sustainability dimensions in the context of career choice do not concern young people alone, but also relate to stakeholders within the VET system. A case in point is companies' willingness to offer apprenticeship places, which is shaped by environmental, social and economic considerations alike. From the companies' perspective, trade-offs may arise between (a) the possibility of deploying apprentices efficiently as skilled workers in the long term, (b) the collective responsibility to provide inclusive training for the next generation, and (c) the use of resources within planetary boundaries. At the same time, interactions between the three

dimensions also create opportunities for companies, for example where a more sustainability-oriented curriculum facilitates the recruitment of apprentices.

Summary and outlook

Within Swiss VET, sustainability has evolved into a key area of policy that takes an integrated approach to the environmental, social and economic dimensions. The environmental dimension centres on the responsible management of natural resources, emission reduction and environmental education. The social dimension highlights equal opportunities, health, inclusion and social cohesion, whereas the economic dimension seeks to strengthen long-term competitiveness, capacity for innovation and the availability of skilled labour.

In the literature considered as part of the OBS trend monitoring activities, the megatrend of sustainability has steadily gained in importance in recent years. Integrating sustainability into curricula and training practice contributes to the development of a VET system that is becoming more environmentally responsible, socially equitable and economically viable, as illustrated by several examples. Trade-offs may arise, however, when environmental considerations in career decisions are overridden by social and economic factors. Using the example of the career choice process, it has been shown that the sustainable transformation of the economy also presents opportunities for VET. This is the case, for example, when environmentally motivated young people are attracted to certain occupations and subsequently help to alleviate skills shortages in a sector, thereby contributing to its long-term economic viability. For companies, it is therefore relevant to explore ways of actively shaping this transformation while minimising potential trade-offs between the different dimensions.

The collective governance model of Swiss VET, jointly supported by the federal government, the cantons and professional organisations, provides a solid framework in principle for achieving sustainability objectives and systematically promoting relevant competences. In light of the scientifically documented urgency of developing measures to address the overshooting of environmental limits, greater discussion is needed on how sustainability can be embedded more holistically within VET by the various stakeholders involved. A fundamental aim is to enable apprentices to recognise, weigh up and respond constructively to trade-offs between the sustainability dimensions. In this respect, VET also holds potential to anchor sustainability more firmly through education for sustainable development. This calls for action not only from the state, but also from companies and education institutions.

References

- [1] Gattlen, N., Klaus, G., & Litsios, G. (2017). Biodiversität in der Schweiz: Zustand und Entwicklung: *Ergebnisse des Überwachungssystems im Bereich Biodiversität, Stand 2016*. Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU.
- [2] European Environment Agency & Federal Office for the Environment (2020). Is Europe living within the limits of our planet? An assessment of Europe's environmental footprints in relation to planetary boundaries. EEA Report No 01/2020.
- [3] SERI (2025). Chancengerechtigkeit im BFI-Bereich. Übersicht über Massnahmen und Aktivitäten mit Schwerpunkt Chancengerechtigkeit. <https://www.sbfli.admin.ch/dam/de/sd-web/MNuVzY9OsoOm/Chancengerechtigkeit%20DE.pdf>.
- [4] Meili, R., Spescha, A., Stucki, T., & Wörter, M. (2025). Statusbericht der Schweizer Kreislaufwirtschaft 2024. *KOF Studies*, 184. <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/items/2ac0412f-924e-4879-ad65-85675cfe9b3d>.
- [5] Swiss Federal Council (2021). Strategie Nachhaltige Entwicklung 2030. Bern, 23 June 2021.
- [6] Kuhlmeier, W., & Vollmer, T. (2018). Ansatz einer Didaktik der Beruflichen Bildung für nachhaltige Entwicklung. In: T. Tramm; M. Casper & T. Schlömer (Hrsg.), *Didaktik der beruflichen Bildung – Selbstverständnis, Zukunftsperspektiven und Innovationsschwerpunkte*, (pp. 131–151). Bonn: Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training.
- [7] Busemeyer, M. R., & Trampusch, C. (2012). The Comparative Political Economy of Collective Skill Formation. In: M. R. Busemeyer (ed.), *The political economy of collective skill formation*, (pp. 3–38). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [8] Busemeyer, M. R., Carstensen, M. B., Kemmerling, A., & Tosun, J. (2025). Foundations for a green economy: how institutions shape green skills. *npj Climate Action*, 4(1), 1–5. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44168-025-00234-5>.
- [9] UNEP/ILO/IOE/ITUC (2008). Green jobs: towards decent work in a sustainable, low-carbon world: Report for the United Nations Environment Programme. *UNEP: Nairobi, Kenya*.
- [10] OECD (2024). OECD Employment Outlook 2024. The Net-Zero Transition and the Labour Market, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/ac8b3538-en>.
- [11] Lobsiger, M., & Rutzer, C. (2021). The green potential of occupations in Switzerland. *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics*, 157(1), 1–21. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s41937-021-00076-y>.
- [12] Federal Office for the Environment & Federal Office of Energy (2020). Jeder Beruf zählt! Umwelt-, Klima- und Energiekompetenzen für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung. Published by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) and the Federal Office of Energy (SFOE).
- [13] Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung (Hrsg.) (2021). *VIER SIND DIE ZUKUNFT: DIGITALISIERUNG. NACHHALTIGKEIT. RECHT. SICHERHEIT. Die modernisierten Standardberufsbildpositionen anerkannter Ausbildungsberufe*. Bonn: Verlag Barbara Budrich.
- [14] Duemmler, K., Widmer, L., & Delanoë, A. (2024). Wie Lernende Nachhaltigkeit im Beruf erleben. *Skilled*, 24(2).
- [15] Adecco Gruppe Schweiz & Swiss Job Market Monitor (2024). Fachkraeftemangel Index 2024. University of Zurich. https://www.adeccogroup.com/de-CH/-/media/project/adecco-group/switzerland/swiss-skills-shortage/2024/files/fachkraeftemangel_index_2024.pdf.

- [16] UNESCO (2022). Transforming technical and vocational education and training for successful and just transitions (2022–2029).
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000383360/PDF/383360eng.pdf.multi>.
- [17] United Nations (1987). Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future. New York: United Nations.
- [18] SERI (2020). Orientierungshilfe nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Berufsbildung. Bern.
<https://www.sbfi.admin.ch/dam/de/sd-web/UbKYLJYYuvGG/Orientierungshilfe%20Nachhaltige%20Entwicklung%20in%20der%20Berufsbildung.pdf>.
- [19] Kitzmann, N., Levke, C., Sakschewski, B., Rockström, J., Andersen, L., Bechthold, M., Bergfeld, L., Beusen, A., Billing, M., Bodirsky, B. L., & others (2025). Planetary Health Check 2025: A Scientific Assessment of the State of the Planet.
- [20] Barbier, E. B. (1987). The Concept of Sustainable Economic Development. *Environmental Conservation*, 14(2), 101–110.
- [21] Nagel, S. (2023). Nachhaltigkeitsorientierte Facharbeit in industriellen Metallberufen: empirische Exploration, Kompetenzmodellierung und Perspektiven für die berufliche Bildung. wbv Media.
- [22] Beer, M. (2020). Berufsbildung für eine nachhaltige Entwicklung am Beispiel des Ausbildungsberufs Milchtechnologin/Milchtechnologe – Der Modellversuch NaMiTec, HiBiFo–Haushalt in Bildung und Forschung, 9(3), 65-80. .
- [23] Hemkes, B., & Melzig, C. (2021). Auf dem Weg vom Projekt zur Struktur – Erkenntnisse zur Verankerung von Nachhaltigkeit aus den BIBB-Modellversuchen zur BBNE. *BWP - Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, (3), 20–23.
- [24] BCH (2017). Modular aufgebaute BNE über die ganze Lehrzeit. *Folio*, (5), 10–11.
- [25] Grundmann, S., & Langen, N. (2024). Gegen den Trend: Prüfung & Kritische Reflexion von Zero-Waste Empfehlungen aus Sicht der Bildung für Nachhaltige Ernährung. *bwp@ Spezial*, HT2023. https://www.bwpat.de/ht2023/grundmann_langen_ht2023.pdf.
- [26] Évéquoz, G. (2020). Die Entwicklung neuer Berufe jenseits der Digitalisierung. *Panorama*, (1), 4–5.
- [27] Baghioni, L., & Moncel, N. (2023). Die ökologische Transformation am Arbeitsplatz. Beschäftigung und Berufsbildung angesichts der Umweltherausforderungen. *BWP – Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, (4), 27–31.
- [28] Trede, I., Hänni, M., Leumann, S., Neumann, J., Gehret, A., Schweri, J., & Kriesi, I. (2020). Berufsmaturität: Bildungsverläufe, Herausforderungen und Potenziale 3. *Trendbericht des Observatoriums für Berufsbildung. Zollikofen: Swiss Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training*.
- [29] Heinemann, A. M. (2023). „Die Kunst des Lehrers kompliziert zu denken“ – über die Notwendigkeit einer differenzsensiblen Professionalisierung in der beruflichen Bildung. *bwp@ Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik - online*, Special issue PH-AT2: Diversität in der Berufsbildung in Österreich, Deutschland und der Schweiz – Perspektiven aus Forschung, Entwicklung und Bildungspraxis, ed. by Albert, S./Heinrichs, K./Hotarek, I./Zenz, pp., 1-17. Online: https://www.bwpat.de/spezial-ph-at2/heinemann_bwpat-ph-at2.pdf.
- [30] Brussino, O. (2021). Building capacity for inclusive teaching: Policies and practices to prepare all teachers for diversity and inclusion. *OECD Education Working Papers* No 256.
- [31] Hupka-Brunner, S., & Meyer, T. (2024). Wie das Geschlecht die Berufswahl und die Karriere beeinflusst. Befunde aus der TREE-Studie (Transitionen von der Erstausbildung ins Erwerbsleben). *Transfer. Berufsbildung in Forschung und Praxis* 9(8).

- [32] Kohaut, S., & Möller, I. (2023). Führungspositionen in Deutschland 2022: Frauen bleiben nach wie vor unterrepräsentiert. *IAB-Kurzbericht* No 22. Nuremberg: Institute for Employment Research (IAB).
- [33] Delautre, G., & Abriata, B. D. (2018). Corporate Social Responsibility: Exploring determinants and complementarities. *ILO Research Department Working Paper*, No 38.
- [34] Slopinski, A., Porath, J., & Krizan, G. M. (2020). Nachhaltigkeit in der Lebenswelt Betrieb – Verständnis, Wahrnehmung und Relevanz von Corporate Social Responsibility aus Sicht In: *bwp@ Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik – online*, Issue 38, 1–20. Online: https://www.bwpat.de/ausgabe38/slopinski_etal_bwpat38.pdf.
- [35] Hiller, B., & Kaufmann, A. (2023). Grüne Wärme – eine Herausforderung für Ausbildungsberufe? *BWP – Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, (4), 22–26.
- [36] Brixy, U., Janser, M., & Mense, A. (2023). Ausbildungsmarkt und ökologische Transformation Auszubildende entscheiden sich zunehmend für Berufe mit umweltfreundlichen Tätigkeiten. *IAB-Kurzbericht*, 19|2023.
- [37] Lehnert, P., & Pfeifer, H. (2024). Environmental Awareness and Occupational Choices of Adolescents. University of Zurich, IBW – Institute of Business Administration, University of Zurich.
- [38] Buschfeld, D., & Menzer, L. (2024). Wer? Wie? Was? Warum? – Wir (be-)fragen potenzielle Handwerksauszubildende und Studierende zu 'Nachhaltigkeit & Beruf'. *bwp@ Spezial HT2023*. <https://kups.ub.uni-koeln.de/75229/>.
- [39] Krummen, M. (2025). Nachhaltige Entwicklung in der Schweizer Landwirtschaft. Sichtweisen von Lernenden des Berufs Landwirt/Landwirtin. Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training (SFUVET).
- [40] Bernhard, U., Joss, M., Rudaz, M., & Heger, M. (2020). Umweltberufe – Ein Wegweiser im Dschungel der Berufs- und Studienwahl.
- [41] SwissSkills (2023). Erwartungen der Gen Z an die Arbeitswelt. Was sind entscheidende Faktoren für die längerfristige Gewinnung, Entwicklung und Bindung von 18- bis 27-jährigen Talenten in der Schweiz? SwissSkills Studie 2023.
- [42] Goller, D., Gschwendt, C., & Wolter, S. C. (2025). This time it's different – Generative artificial intelligence and occupational choice. *Labour Economics*, 95, 102746.
- [43] Kuczera, M. (2025). Vocational education and training (VET) and the green transition: Insights from labour market data. *OECD Social, Employment, and Migration Working Papers*, No 327.
- [44] Carstensen, M. B., Ibsen, C. L., & Jensen, I. M. N. (2024). Integrating ecosocial policies through polycentric governance: A study of the green transformation of Danish vocational education and training. *Regulation & Governance*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rego.12633>
- [45] Kammermann, M., Scharnhorst, U., & Balzer, L. (2015). Die zweijährigen beruflichen Grundbildungen in der Schweiz: Welches Inklusionspotenzial haben sie. *BWP-Berufsbildung in Wissenschaft und Praxis*, 44(2), 15–19.
- [46] Lamamra, N., Duc, B., Romanens, M., & Descloux, G. (2025). Gesundheit von Lernenden: Zwischen Schutzgedanken und Risikoverharmlosung. *Transfer. Berufsbildung in Forschung und Praxis*, 10(8).
- [47] Olsson, D., & Gericke, N. (2016). The adolescent dip in students' sustainability consciousness—Implications for education for sustainable development. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 47(1), 35–51.
- [48] Uitto, A., & Saloranta, S. (2010). The relationship between secondary school students' environmental and human values, attitudes, interests and motivations. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 9, 1866–1872.

Suggested citation

Pusterla, F., Hänni, M., & Graf, L. (2026). *Environmental, social and economic sustainability as a trend in vocational education and training*. OBS SFUVET Trends in Focus No 16. Zollikofen: Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training SFUVET.

Swiss Observatory for Vocational Education
and Training OBS SFUVET

Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education
and Training SFUVET

Kirchlindachstrasse 79

3052 Zollikofen

Switzerland

+41 58 458 27 00

obs@ehb.swiss

<https://www.sfuvet.swiss/research/obs>